

Synthesis of Some Substituted(3*N*-aminomethyl-1'-phenyl-4'-amino)substituted phenyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolones as Antiamoebic Agents

PRAMILA SHAH, V. K. SAXENA and V. S. MISRA*

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 3 August 1982, revised 7 May 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

Thirty two new substituted(3*N*-aminomethyl-1'-phenyl-4'-amido)substituted phenyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolones were synthesised and screened for *in vitro* amoebicidal activity against the axenic culture of *Entamoeba histolytica*. Some of these compounds have displayed significant amoebicidal activity at a concentration of 125 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

IN continuation with our previous work¹, some newer 4(3*H*)-quinazolone derivatives have been synthesised and evaluated for amoebicidal activity. A large number of compounds having the quinazolone ring system have shown CNS^{2,3}, anticonvulsant^{4,5}, amoebicidal⁶⁻⁸ and hypnotic⁹ activity.

The preparation of these substituted (3*N*-aminomethyl-1'-phenyl-4'-amido)substituted phenyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolones (3) involved various steps. First, substituted 3*N*-aminomethyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolones (1) were synthesised from substituted-4(3*H*)-quinazolones. These aminomethyl quinazolones were then treated with an aromatic carboxylic acid, *i.e.* *p*-chlorobenzoic acid to yield substituted 3*N*-aminomethyl-1'-arylcarboxylic-4(3*H*)-quinazolones (2). The different acids so obtained were converted to their acid chlorides by treating with thionyl chloride in presence of dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate. The respective acid chlorides were then treated with simple and substituted aromatic amines to give the compounds (3).

Experimental

Melting points of all the compounds were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Pmr spectra were carried out at a frequency of 90 MHz in DMSO-*d*₆ medium.

4(3*H*)-quinazolone, 6-bromo- and 6,8-dibromo-quinazolone: These were prepared according to the method of Endicott *et al.*¹⁰.

6-Nitro-4(3*H*)-quinazolone: This was synthesised by the previously reported method¹¹.

Substituted 3*N*-aminomethyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolones (1): These were synthesised according to the method of Mukerji *et al.*¹².

Substituted 3*N*-aminomethyl-1'-arylcarboxylic-4(3*H*)-quinazolones (2): These were prepared by the previously reported method¹.

Substituted (3*N*-aminomethyl-1'-phenyl-4'-amido)substituted phenyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolones (3): The acids (2) so prepared were then treated with an equimolar quantity of thionyl chloride in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate. The mixture was refluxed for 2-2.5 h. The acid chlorides so obtained were not isolated, but immediately an appropriate amine (0.1 mol) was added to the freshly prepared acid chlorides. The mixture was finally refluxed for 4-5 h on a steam-bath. The excess acetone was distilled off and then methanol was added. The mixture was again heated so that the compound dissolved leaving the potassium carbonate behind. Excess methanol was distilled off and the flask kept overnight in an ice-box. Compounds 1-3, 13, 17-19 were then recovered by the addition of concentrated HCl (3-4 drops). Compounds 4-11, 12, 14-16, 20-32 were recovered by addition of water and concentrated HCl (1:2). The compounds were finally crystallised from methanol. Thus, thirty two new compounds were synthesised and their analytical data given in Table 1.

Ir spectra: The compounds show intense bands at 1642 ($\text{O}=\text{C}=\text{NH}-$), 1680 ($\text{O}=\overset{\text{I}}{\text{C}}-\text{OH}$), 1500 (NO_2) and 600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{Br}$).

Pmr spectra: In pmr spectra of these substituted 4(3*H*)-quinazolones, singlet due to methylene protons were observed around δ 2.32 for $-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}$ and multiplet at 6.0-8.40 for the aromatic protons.

Pharmacological study: All the compounds were evaluated for the *in vitro* amoebicidal activity against *Entamoeba histolytica* (strain NIH 200) by the method of Das and Prasad¹³ at pH 6.7. Since acidic pH is favourable for the growth of the amoebae, culture of *E. histolytica* was maintained in modified TPS-1 medium by the method of Singh

TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTED(3*N*-AMINOMETHYL-1'-PHENYL-4'-AMIDO)SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-4(3*H*)-QUINAZOLONES (3)*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Yield %
1.	H	H	H	197-198	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	65
2.	H	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	182-188	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	64
3.	H	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	216-218	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	60
4.	H	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	200-201	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl.2HCl	61
5.	H	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	192-194	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	65
6.	H	H	<i>p</i> -OH ₃	212-214	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	63
7.	H	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	196-198	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl.2HCl	55
8.	H	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	187-189	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	60
9.	Br	H	H	257-258	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	64
10.**	Br	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	178-180	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	60
11.	Br	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	194-196	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	68
12.	Br	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	183-184	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr.2HCl	70
13.**	Br	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	138-139	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	65
14.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	149-151	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr.2HCl	60
15.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	157-159	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	65
16.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	194-196	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	64
17.	Br	H	2-OCH ₃ -4NO ₂	196-197	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br.2HCl	63
18.	Br	Br	H	163-164	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	61
19.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	198-200	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	60
20.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	194-195	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	65
21.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -Cl	209-211	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr ₂ .2HCl	68
22.	Br	Br	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	148-150	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	63
23.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	260 (d)	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	60
24.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -Cl	216-218	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr ₂ .2HCl	65
25.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	190-192	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	62
26.	NO ₂	H	H	226-228	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	63
27.**	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	270-271	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	62
28.	NO ₂	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	182-183	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	61
29.	NO ₂	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	240-242	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl.2HCl	60
30.**	NO ₂	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	270 (d)	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	65
31.	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	238-240	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl.2HCl	65
32.	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	221-223	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ .2HCl	70

* C, H, N found within ± 0.4% of theoretical values.

** Displayed amoebicidal activity at 125 µg ml⁻¹ (m.i.c.).

*et al.*¹⁴ and subsequent sub-cultures were made by inoculating 100000 amoebae from 72-96 h old culture to fresh TPS-1 media in 16×125 mm rubber lined screw capped tubes. The tubes were incubated at 37° in an upright position and the growth of the amoebae was observed under an inverted microscope. A clear stock solution of the test compound was prepared in distilled water with the help of dimethylformamide (DMF) to give a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. 1 ml of this solution was added to 7 ml of distilled water and DMF to give a final volume of 8 ml. This gave the working concentration as 1250 µg ml⁻¹. While preparing the drug dilutions, care was taken in the addition of DMF, so that in the final volume (8 ml) DMF did not exceed 1.5 ml. 1.25% DMF in the test solution is toxic for *E. histolytica*. The tubes were then sterilised by autoclaving at 15 psi pressure for 15 min.

To 8 ml of TPS-1 medium dispersed in 16×125 mm rubber lined screw capped tubes, 1 ml of drug dilution was added. The tubes were allowed to

stand overnight in upright position in an incubator at 37°. 1 ml of amoebic inoculum was added to the tubes and the tubes were again incubated. Amoebicidal action of each compound was then determined under an inverted microscope after 72 h. Serial drug dilutions were prepared, *i.e.* 62.5, 31.25, 15.62, and 7.81 µg ml⁻¹, respectively and the amoebicidal activity was noted. Controls were also kept which included the amoebic inoculum and TPS-1 medium but no drug dilution. Emetine hydrochloride and Metronidazole were used as the standard drugs. The former was effective at 62.5 and the latter at 7.8 µg ml⁻¹ under the above mentioned conditions.

Results and Discussion

Four compounds, 10, 13, 27 and 30 (Table 1) were active only at 125 µg ml⁻¹ (m.i.c.) when tested under the above mentioned conditions. At lower dilutions, *i.e.* 62.5, 31.25, µg ml⁻¹ *etc.* no death of amoebae occurred.

On examining the structure of these compounds it is apparent that the presence of active groups, *i.e.* methoxy, bromo and nitro is probably responsible for the activity in these compounds. However, when two bromo groups are present in the quinazolone ring system, the activity gets lost. A single bromo or a methoxy or a nitro substituent has shown its effect by being amoebicidal at 125 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, Dr. S. K. Gupta, Head, Microbiology Division, C.D.R.I., Dr. B. N. K. Prasad, C.D.R.I., and (Miss) Indu Bansal, C.D.R.I. for the elemental and spectral analysis, and biological screening of the compounds. One of the authors (V. K. S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. V. S. MISRA, V. K. SAXENA and P. SHAH, *Indian Drugs*, 1981, 18, 276.
2. K. NODA, A. NAKAGAWA, Z. S. YAMA, K. NOGUCHI, T. HACHIYA and H. IDE, *Jap. Pat.* 7778888 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 68088).
3. S. SATO and G. TSUKAMOTO, *Jap. Pat.* 76133287 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 68405).
4. W. BOGGANI, J. B. MEYER, R. M. STEINBERG and C. WASHINGTON, *Psychopharmacol. (Berlin)*, 1977, 54, 45.
5. T. MICHIMIRO and M. SHIGRAKI, *Jap. Pat.*, 74110681.
6. R. C. GUPTA, R. NATH, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 219.
7. M. SHARMA, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHOR, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1979, 41, 44.
8. H. NESVADBA and H. REINSHAGEN, *Belg. Pat.* 841669/1976 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 135380).
9. L. ZHELYAKOV, R. KOLCHAGOVA, D. STEFANOVA and L. DALEVA, *Tr. Nauchn. Khim. Farm. Inst.*, 1972, 8, 729.
10. M. ENDICOTT, E. WICK, M. L. MERCURY and M. L. SHERRILL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1299, ST. VON NIEMENOWSKI, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1895, 51, 564.
11. M. T. BOBERT and G. A. GRIGER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 524.
12. D. D. MUKERJI and S. R. NAUTIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1226.
13. S. R. DAS and B. N. K. PRASAD, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, 42, 796.
14. B. N. SINGH, S. R. DASS and G. P. DUTTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, 42, 227.